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An Assessment Of The Reformative And Rehabilitative Rights Of The Nigerian Inmates: The Thrust Of Modern Penological Objectives

Tamunoemi A. Abbiyesuku*

***LL.B (Hons), LL.M (RSU), BL (Abuja), Ph.D Research Candidate (RSU),**

**Senior Lecturer, Department of Law,
School of Legal Studies,**

**Port Harcourt Polytechnic, Rumuola, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria.
tamunoemi.abbiyesuku@portharcourtpoly.edu.ng, 08037632537.**

ABSTRACT

The Nigerian inmates while serving their correctional term do not lose their rights to the basic necessities of life. Notwithstanding the incarceration, their rights to reformation, rehabilitation and reintegration back into the society to lead a crime free life and its basic components are guaranteed and protected by the relevant correctional laws. This article assessed the reformative and rehabilitative rights of the Nigerian inmates as the thrust of modern penological objectives. The rights of the Nigerian inmates to education/vocational training, development, recreation/leisure, work/wages and communication with the outside world which are the derivatives of the right of the Nigerian inmates to reformation and rehabilitation were examined. The principal aim of this article is to assess the reformative and rehabilitative rights of Nigerian inmates as the thrust of modern penological objectives and make a case for reform, while the specific objective is to identify the rights implicit in the right to reformation and rehabilitation of the Nigerian inmates in accordance with the legal frameworks protecting these rights. The doctrinal legal research methodology was adopted and reliance was made extensively on primary and secondary source of information, with the utilization of international, regional and domestic laws, including case laws, among others. This article finds that the right of the Nigerian inmates to reformation and rehabilitation has been contravened in several areas, such as non-provision of adequate vocational training and educational facilities for inmates, deprivation of work/wages on certain inmates, non-provision of adequate recreational activities/leisure for inmates and so on. It is the further finding of this article that the lack of proper reformation and rehabilitation of the Nigerian inmates is the engine room of recidivism of the inmates in Nigeria. This article concludes that the Nigerian Correctional Service saddled with the responsibility of implementing the Nigerian inmates right to reformation and rehabilitation should act swiftly in order to curb further violations of the Nigerian inmates' rights to rehabilitation, reformation and reintegration back to the society. Therefore, this article recommends that adequate provisions should be made for the educational and vocational training of inmates in the Nigerian correctional centres which should be integrated into public schools and educational system of the country to enable the inmates to continue in their education and vocational training even after release without difficulty.

Keywords: Rights, Inmates, Reformation, Rehabilitation, Reintegration, Education/Vocational Training.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The modern thrust of penological objectives is the introduction of the right to reformation, rehabilitation and reintegration of the inmates back into the society in our correctional laws.¹ The Nigerian inmates are persons incarcerated in lawful custody as a result of custodial judgment of being in contravention with the law, who may be convicted or awaiting trial.² The Nigerian inmates are persons held in lawful custody for violating the laws of the State for the modern penological thrust of reformation, rehabilitation and reintegration back to the society.³ The right to reformation and rehabilitation of the Nigerian inmates remains the goal of the modern penological system.

Consequently, the incarceration of inmates in the Nigerian correctional centres is not a deprivation of their basic rights, particularly, the right to reformation, rehabilitation and reintegration into the society to lead a crime free life. Accordingly, subject to certain limitations by virtue of their incarceration, the Nigerian inmates' rights to reformation and rehabilitation, like other rights, are guaranteed by the law.⁴ Again, implicit in the rights of the Nigerian inmates to reformation, rehabilitation and reintegration into the society are the rights to education/vocational training,⁵ development,⁶ recreation/leisure,⁷ work/wages,⁸ including communication with the outside world. The contraventions of any of these rights amount to an infringement on the Nigerian inmates' rights to reformation, rehabilitation and reintegration back into the society to lead a crime free life which is the modern thrust of confinement into the correctional centres or facilities. This article therefore assessed the reformatory and rehabilitation rights of the Nigerian inmates as the modern thrust of penological objectives.

2.0 Right to Reformation and Rehabilitation

The modern thrust of penal policy is the inculcation of the right to reformation and rehabilitation of inmates.⁹ The right to reformation and rehabilitation of inmates remains the goal of many penal policy makers in Africa.¹⁰ Thus, offenders are sent to correctional centres to rehabilitate them, so that they no

¹ Nigerian Correctional Service Act 2019, ss 2(1)(c), 4(2)(6), 10(e)(d), 14; Administration Criminal Justice Act 2015, ss 311(2)(a), 401(2)(c), 460(4)(b); Ouagadougou Declaration and Plan of Action on Accelerating Prison and Penal Reform in Africa 2002, paras 1, 3; United Nations Standard Minimum Rule for the Treatment of Prisoners 2015, r 4(1)(2).

² NCSA (n1) s 46.

³ T A Abbiyesuku, 'Accessing the Rights of the Nigerian Inmates to Access to Justice', Conference Paper Presented at the 1st International Conference of Law of the Faculty of Law, Gombe State University on Law, Society and Sustainable Development: Emerging Issues in Environmental and Energy Governance, held at Haruna Rashid Hall, Gombe State University, Tudun Wada, Gombe State Nigeria, 17-18 February, 2026, 2.

⁴ T A Abbiyesuku, 'A Critical Analysis of the Institutional Frameworks Protecting the Rights of Inmates in Nigeria' [2005](22)(1) *Journal of Private and Property Law, Rivers State University*, 2; T A Abbiyesuku, 'A Comparative Disclosure of Judicial Craftsmanship in Protecting the Rights of Inmates in Nigeria, India, South Africa and United States of America' [2025](5)(3) *Journal of Law and Policy, Rivers State University, Port Harcourt*, 187; T A Abbiyesuku, 'An Appraisal of the Legal Frameworks Protecting the Rights of Inmates in Nigeria', Conference Paper Presented at the 1st International Conference of Law of the Faculty of Law, Gombe State University on Law, Society and Sustainable Development: Emerging Issues in Environmental and Energy Governance, held at Haruna Rashid Hall, Gombe State University, Tudun Wada, Gombe State Nigeria, 17-18 February, 2026, 2, 32.

⁵ Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended), s 18(1)(3); African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (Rectification and Enforcement Act) 1983, art 17(1); NCSA (n1) ss 10(h), 14; Kampala Declaration on Prison Condition in Africa 1996, para 7; Universal Declaration on Human Rights 1948, art 26(1); International Covenant Economic, Social and Cultural Rights 1966, art 13(1); UNSMR (n1) rr 4(2), 98(1), 104; United Nations Body of Principles for the Protection of All Persons Under Any Form of Detention or Imprisonment 1988, prin 28.

⁶ ACHPR(n5) art 22; United Nations Declaration on the Right to Development 1986, arts 1, 2(1), 8(1); United Nations Basic Principles for the Treatment of Prisons 1990, prin 6.

⁷ CFRN(n5) s 17(3)(d); Nigeria Prison Service Standing Orders 2011, ords 381(a)(e), 387; UDHR (n5) art 24; UNSMR (n1) rr 23, 105.

⁸ CFRN (n5) s 17(3)(a)(b); NCSA (n1) ss 10(h), 14(1)(3)(4)(a); ACHPR (n5) art 15; NPSSO (n7) ord 167; UDHR (n5) art 23; ICESCR (n5) arts 5, 7; UNSMR (n1) rr 96, 98; Basic Principles (n6) prin 8.

⁹ V V Tarhule, 'Synoptic Appraisal of the Nigerian Correctional Service Act 2019' [2019/2020] *Benue State University Journal of Law*, 2.

¹⁰ J Sarkin, 'Prisons in Africa: An Evaluation from A human Rights Perspective' [2008](5)(9) *International Journal on Human Rights*, 31.

longer need to commit crimes.¹¹ The right to reformation and rehabilitation has become part of the process of enabling the inmates to make positive choices.¹² The rehabilitative and reformatory rights are the measures taken to change an inmates character, habit or behaviour patterns, so as to diminish his criminal propensities.¹³ This right is aimed to transform the inmates into good, honest and law abiding citizens by inculcating in them a distaste for crime and criminality.¹⁴ The rehabilitative and reformatory ideals teaches that each inmate must be treated as an individual whose special need and problem must be known as fully as possible in order to effectively deal with him.¹⁵ Accordingly, the contemporary panel system advocates rehabilitation and reformation as the justification for imprisonment.¹⁶ Evidently, the thrust for the rehabilitative and reformatory rights of the inmates is to re-socialize and reform the inmates and make them better and law abiding citizens aimed at reintegrating them into the society.

Consequently, the right of the Nigerian inmates to rehabilitation and reformation is protected under the Nigerian correctional service Act,¹⁷ Administration of Criminal Justice Act,¹⁸ Ouagadougou Declaration¹⁹ and United Nations Standard Minimum Rules.²⁰ Thus, Section 2(1)(c) of the NCSA opined that, ‘the objective of the correctional service is to enhance the focus on corrections and promotion of reformation, rehabilitation and reintegration of inmates. Section 4(2)(b) of the NCSA also empowers the Controller General of the Nigerian Correctional Service oversee the reformation, rehabilitation and reintegration of inmates. Moreso, the custodial service is empowered to conducting risk and need assessment aimed at developing appropriate correctional treatment methods for reformation, rehabilitation and reintegration of inmates and implementing reformation and rehabilitation programmes to enhance the reintegration of inmates back to the society.²¹ Further, Section 311(2)(a) of the ACJA opined that, ‘the court shall in pronouncing sentence consider reformation of the inmates as its objective of sentencing’. Section 401(2)(c) of the ACJA adumbrates that, ‘in the determination of a sentence, the court shall have in its mind the objective of rehabilitation of the inmates, that is the objective of providing the inmates with treatment or training that will make them into a reformed citizens’. Moreso, the court in exercising its power in ordering suspended sentence and community service shall have regard to the need to rehabilitate inmates by making them to undertake productive work.²²

Consequently, at the African scene, the Ouagadougou Declaration calls for the promotion of rehabilitation and reintegration of inmates.²³ alluding to this, the United Nations Standard Minimum Rules has opined that, ‘the purpose of sentence of imprisonment is to use the period of imprisonment to ensure as far as possible the rehabilitation and reintegration of inmates into society upon release so that they can Lead a law-abiding and Self-supporting life’.²⁴ Accordingly, the philosophy of the Nigerian Correctional Service is that the treatment and rehabilitation of inmates can be achieved through care designed and well-articulated administrative, reformatory and rehabilitative measures.²⁵

¹¹ K S Adebisi, ‘Prisons and Security Challenges in a Democratic Nigeria’ [2015](5)(6) *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences*, 124.

¹² G Robinson, ‘Late-Modern Rehabilitation’ [2008](10) *Punishment & Modern Society*, 433.

¹³ A V Hirsch, *Doing Justice the choice of Punishment: Report of the Committee for the Study of Incarceration* (Hill and Wang 1976) 11.

¹⁴ Y A Muhammed and Others ‘The Right of Prisoners in Nigeria and the Role of Prisoners and Modern Penology’ [2017](60) *Journal of Law, Policy and Globalization*, 79.

¹⁵ J Kaplan, *Criminal Justice: Introductory Cases and Materials* (2nd end, Foundation Press 1978) 26.

¹⁶ M S Afolanya, ‘Development of Private Prisons in Advance Countries: Prospects for Nigeria’ in *Essays in Honour of Professor Ifedayo Timothy Akomotode* (The Law Society of the Faculty of Law, Ekiti State University 2014) 73.

¹⁷ NCSA (n1) ss 2(1)(c), 4(2)(6), 10(e)(d), 14.

¹⁸ ACJA (n1) ss 311(2)(a), 401(2)(c), 460(4)(b).

¹⁹ Ouagadougou Declaration (n1) paras 1, 3.

²⁰ UNSMR (n1) r 4(1)(2).

²¹ NCSA (n1) s 10(e)(f).

²² ACJA (n1) 546(4)(b).

²³ Ouagadougou Declaration (n1) para 3.

²⁴ UNSMR (n1) r 4(1).

²⁵ N J Aduba, ‘Overcrowding in Nigeria Prisons: A Critical Appraisal’ [1993] *Journal of criminal Justice*, 185.

Thus, the right to reformation and rehabilitation is to ensure that inmates are reformed and re-socialized to be reintegrated back to the society to lead law abiding and criminal free life. Implicit and connected to the right of reformation and rehabilitation is the right to education/vocational training, development, recreation/leisure, work/wages and communication with the outside world. These rights shall be examined.

2.1 Right to Education/Vocational Training

The rights of the Nigerian inmates to education/vocational training implicit in the right of reformation and rehabilitation is protected under the Nigerian constitution,²⁶ African Charter,²⁷ Nigerian Correctional Service Act²⁸ and Nigerian Prison Service Standing Orders.²⁹ Thus, Section 18(1) of the CFRN opined that, 'Government shall direct its policy towards ensuring that there are equal and adequate educational opportunities at all levels'. Article 17(1) of the ACHPR also adumbrates that, 'every individual shall have the right to education'. Moreso, section 10(h) of the NCSA empowers the correctional service to empowering inmates through the deployment of educational and vocational skills training programmes. Further, section 14(1) of the NCSA opined that, 'the correctional service shall provide opportunities for education, vocational training, as well as training in modern farming techniques and animal husbandry for inmates. Accordingly, the correctional service shall establish and run in designated custodial centres, industrial centres equipped with modern facilities for the enhancement of vocational skills training for inmates aimed at facilitating their reintegration into society.³⁰ Moreso, by virtue of section 381(a) of the NCSA education activities shall be provided for convicted inmates and young persons in custody. Consequently, the education of inmates shall be integrated with the national educational system so as to enable them continue the education without difficulty after their release.³¹ Accordingly, the Nigerian Correctional Service shall employ qualified teachers and instructors to teach and educate inmates in corroboration with appropriate educational institutions.³²

The right of the Nigerian inmate to education/vocational training are further guaranteed at the regional and international front by the Kampala Declaration,³³ Universal Declaration of Human Rights,³⁴ International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights,³⁵ United Nations Standard Minimum Rules³⁶ and United Nations Body of Principles.³⁷ Thus, paragraph 7 of the Kampala Declaration opined that, 'inmates should be given access to education and skill training in order to make it easier for them to reintegrate into the society after their release'. Article 26(1) of the UDHR also adumbrates that, 'everyone has the right to education'. Similarly, Article 13(1) of the ICESCR aver that, 'States parties shall recognize the right of everyone to education'. Moreso, Rule 4(2) of the UNSMR opined, 'that correctional administrations should offer education and vocational training to inmates.' Accordingly, vocational training in useful trades shall be provided for inmates.³⁸ Again, Rule 104(10) of the UNSMR avers that, 'provision shall be made for the further education of all inmates. Consequently, so far as practicable, the education of inmates shall be integrated with the educational system of the country so that after their release they may continue their education without difficulty.³⁹ Further, Principle 28 of the Body of

²⁶ CFRN (n5) s 18(1)(3).

²⁷ ACHPR (n5) art 17(1).

²⁸ NCSA (n1) ss 10(h), 14.

²⁹ NPSSO (n7) ss 158, 38(a)(b)(d), 387.

³⁰ NCSA (n1) s 14(2).

³¹ NPSSO (n7) s 381(b).

³² NPSSO (n7) s 381(d).

³³ Kampala Declaration (n5) Para 7.

³⁴ UDHR (n5) art 26(1).

³⁵ ICESCR (n5) art 13(1).

³⁶ UNSMR (n1) rr 4(2), 98(1), 104.

³⁷ Body of Principles (n5) prin 28.

³⁸ UNSMR (n1) r 98(2).

³⁹ *Ibid*, r 104 (2).

Principles submits that, ‘a detained or imprisoned person shall have the right to obtain reasonable quantities of educational and informational material’.

Thus, education, training and work are central aspects in the life of every individual, including inmates, essential for the conscious construction of their identity and independence.⁴⁰ Education is a public good and fundamental human right that enables the realization of other human rights.⁴¹ Accordingly, denying the right to education, training and development of one’s personality to those who erred is not punishing the inmates for crimes committed, but rather depriving them of relationships, future plans and educational compensation.⁴² It is however conducive to good reasoning to argue that the right to education does not confine only to classroom education but extends to all informal technical and other training that enables individuals acquire the needed skills for economic good.⁴³ The success of education and training programmes is usually concluded in term of reductions in recidivism.⁴⁴ Thus, engaging inmates in higher levels of education provides powerful cognitive and social learning which are fundamental to rehabilitation.⁴⁵ The provision of education addresses the issue of prisonization, whereby inmates become acculturated to the negative values of correctional centres sub-culture.⁴⁶

Connected to the right to education/vocational training of the Nigerian inmates is the right to the provision of a befitting library in the Nigerian correctional centres. The right of the Nigerian inmates to a befitting library is protected under the Nigerian Prisons Service Standing Order⁴⁷ and United Nations Standard Minimum Rules.⁴⁸ Thus, section 392(a) of the NPSSO which is similar in provision with Rule 64 of the UNSMR opined that, ‘there shall be established in all correctional centres a library for the use of all categories of inmates, adequately stock with both recreational and instructional books.’ Evidently, correctional centres library is a special library that provides specialized library services to the inmates and it is to provide varieties of quality information materials in terms of currency, relevance, accuracy and ease of use to meet and satisfy the information needs of the inmates.⁴⁹ Accordingly, the library services to inmates are critical to their rehabilitation into the larger society on release.⁵⁰ Thus, the provision of educational, vocational training and library services are vital to the reformation and rehabilitation of inmates in the Nigerian correctional centres.

However, the National Human Rights Commission has reported that in most of the correctional centres audited vocational facilities are inadequate compared to the number of inmates in the correctional centre’.⁵¹ Besides, there were no educational facilities in the correctional centres audited in the North East Zone of Nigeria.⁵² Amnesty International also reports that, ‘some correctional centres visited offered schooling opportunities to a limited number of convicted inmates, but even these centres lacked sufficient

⁴⁰ F Torlone, ‘The Right to Educational Compensation of the Prisoners in the Halina System’ [1018](8)(4) *Hungarian Educational Research Journal*, 61.

⁴¹ S C Kajamo and L R Johnson, ‘The Right to Education: Is It a Reality or a Pipe Dream for Incarcerated Young Prisoners in Malawi’ [2023](7)(3) *Journal of Prisons Education and Reentry*, 268.

⁴² Torlone (n40).

⁴³ A O Enabulele, ‘The Right to life or the Right to a Decent Burial: The Constitutional Text and Judicial Understanding of the Right to life in Nigeria’ [2012](4)(1) *Port Harcourt Law Journal*, 64.

⁴⁴ H Farley and A Pike, ‘Engaging Prisoners in Education: Reducing Risk and Recidivism’ [2016] *Journal of the International Corrections and Prisons Association*, 68.

⁴⁵ D A Andrews and C Dowden, ‘The Risk-Need Responsibility Model of Assessment and Human Service in Prevention and Corrections: Time Prevention Jurisprudence’ [2007](49)(4) *Canadian Journal of Criminology and Criminal Justice*, 439.

⁴⁶ D Brazzell and others, ‘*From the Classroom to the Community: Exploring the Role of Education During Incarceration and Re-Entry* (The Urban Institute 2009) 47.

⁴⁷ NPSSO (n7) ord 392.

⁴⁸ UNSMR (n1) r 64.

⁴⁹ J K Fasae and F J Folorunson, ‘Prison Libraries and Its Services in Nigeria: An Overview’ [2020] *Library Philosophy and Practice E-Journal*, 4065.

⁵⁰ R N Okwor and Others, ‘Library Services to Prisoners in South East Geopolitical Zones of Nigeria [2010](7)(1) *Information Technologist Journal*, 4.

⁵¹ T Ojukwu and O B Agu (eds), ‘Prison Report 2018’ (National Human Rights Commission Publication 2018) 11.

⁵² *Ibid*, 43.

books, educational supplies and vocational training materials'.⁵³ Moreso, Fasae and Folorunso, has observed that, 'in Nigeria the provision of library services to inmates has been grossly undercut, which has resulted in situations where most prison libraries are left with scanty information resources to support inmates further education and general reading interests'.⁵⁴ Emasealu, has also noted that the provision of library services to correctional centres inmates in Nigeria, 'has been completely undermined leading to unavailability of information resources in prison libraries that should cater for inmates reading interest'.⁵⁵ The Nigerian correctional centres libraries also lacks professional librarians.⁵⁶

These abuse of the non-provision of adequate and functional educational/vocational training facilities in the Nigerian correctional centres contravene the right of the Nigerian inmates to education/vocational training, and the right to a befitting library implicit in the right reformation and rehabilitation protected under the relevant laws.⁵⁷ Again, the express provision of Order 381 of the NPSSO which opined that educational activities shall be provided for only convicted inmates and young persons in custody violates the right to education/vocational training of the inmates on awaiting trial guaranteed under the relevant laws.⁵⁸

2.2 Right to Development

The right of the Nigerian inmates to developments of the human person implicit in the right to reformation and rehabilitation is protected under the African charter,⁵⁹ United Nations Declaration on the Right to Development⁶⁰ and United Nations Basic Principles.⁶¹ Thus, Article 22(1) of the ACHPR opined that, 'all peoples shall have the right to their economic, social and cultural development'. Accordingly, States have the duty to ensure the existence of the right to development.⁶² Article 1(1) of the DRTD also adumbrates that, 'the right to development is an inalienable right by virtue of which every human person and all people are entitled to participate in, contribute to and enjoy economic, social, cultural and political development in which all human rights and fundamental freedoms can be fully realized'. Every human person and all people as used in the law refers also to the Nigerian inmates. The human person is the central subject to development and should be the active participant and beneficiary of the right to development.⁶³ Accordingly, States are under obligation to undertake at the national level all necessary measures for the realization of the right to development and shall ensure, inter alia, equality of opportunity for all in their access to basic resources, education, health services, food housing and so on, and appropriate economic and social reforms which should be carried out with a view to eradicating all social injustice.⁶⁴ Further, by virtue principle 6 of the Basic Principles all inmates shall have the right to take part in cultural activities aimed at the full development of the human personality. Thus, in *Charles Sobhraj v Superintendent Central Jail*,⁶⁵ the Supreme Court of India held that the purpose of imprisonment is not only punitive but also reformatory, and that inmates must be provided with

⁵³ Amnesty International, 'Nigeria: Prisoners' Rights Systematically Flouted' (Amnesty International Publication 2008) 28 <<https://www.amnesty.org/art.44/001/2008/en>> accessed 15 February, 2026.

⁵⁴ Fasae (n49) 5.

⁵⁵ H U Emasealu, 'Information Needs and the Enhancement of the Psychological Well-being of Prison Inmates in Nigeria' [2015] *Library Philosophy and practice E-Journal*, 1365; H U Emasealu, Making Available Library Information Resources for utilization and Reformation of Prison Inmates' [2017](5)(12) *Information and knowledge Management Journal*, 40.

⁵⁶ A S Sambo and Others, 'Prisoners and their Information Needs: Prison Libraries Overview' [2017] *Library Philosophy and Practice E-Journal*, 1467.

⁵⁷ CFRN (n5) s18(1)(3); ACHPR(n5) art 17(1); NCSA (n1) ss10 (h), 14; NPSSO (n7) ords 158, 381(a)(b)(d), 387; Kampala Declaration (n5) para 7; UDHR(n5) art 26(1); ICESCR (n5) art 13(1); UNSMR (n1) r 4(2), 98(1), 104; Body of Principles (n5) prin 28.

⁵⁸ CFRN (n5) s 18(1)(3).

⁵⁹ ACHPR(n5) art 22.

⁶⁰ UNDRD(n6) arts 1, 2(1), 8(1).

⁶¹ Basic Principles (n6) prin 6.

⁶² ACHPR (n5) art 22(2).

⁶³ UNDRD (n6) art 2(1).

⁶⁴ *Ibid*, art 8(1).

⁶⁵ AIR 1978 SC 1514.

opportunities for education, training as well as those for the development of the inmates into a better human being.

The right to development of the Nigerian inmates is paramount to their reformation and rehabilitation to be properly reintegrated into the society. Accordingly, the non-provision of adequate reformation and rehabilitation measures to the Nigerian inmates guaranteed under the relevant laws,⁶⁶ contained in the reports of the National Human Right Commission⁶⁷ and Amnesty International⁶⁸ mentioned earlier, amounts to the infraction of the right to development of the Nigerian inmates, implicit in the right to reformation and rehabilitation protected under the relevant Laws.⁶⁹

2.3 Right to Recreation/Leisure

The right of the Nigerian inmate to recreation/leisure implicit in the right to reformation and rehabilitation is protected under the Nigerian constitution⁷⁰ and Nigerian Prisons Service Standing Orders.⁷¹ Thus, section 17(3)(b) of the CFRN opined that, 'the State shall direct its policy towards ensuring that there are adequate facilities for leisure'. Again, by virtue Order 381(a) of the NPSSO recreational activities shall be provided for convicted inmates and young person in custody. Accordingly, recreational activities shall be provided in all correctional centres for the benefit of the mental and physical health of inmates.⁷²

Further, at the international scene, the right of the Nigerian inmates to recreation and leisure is protected under the Universal Declaration of Human Rights⁷³ and United Nations Standard Minimum Rules.⁷⁴ Thus, Article 24 of the UDHR adumbrates that, 'everyone has the right leisure'. Rule 105 of UNSMR also opined that recreational activities shall be provided in all correctional centres 'for the benefit of the mental and physical health of inmates. Consequently, young inmates and others of suitable age and physique shall receive physical and recreational training during the period of exercise.'⁷⁵

Accordingly, the right to recreation/leisure is to be enjoyed by all inmates in the Nigerian correctional centres and this will make changes to their attitude and behavior.⁷⁶ Recreation/leisure activities help inmates to reduce stress, conquer social weaknesses and encourage physical wellbeing.⁷⁷ Recreation/leisure activities allow inmates to relieve the pressure of life in correctional centres while promoting healthy, physical, mental and social abilities. It also helps inmates to better themselves physically and mentally as individuals.⁷⁸ Thus, the right to recreation and leisure enhances the inmates' self-actualization, self-esteem and self-worth enabling constructive reintegration in to the society.⁷⁹ Accordingly, Carter and Russell have observed that:

Recreation allows inmates to develop acceptable outlets for stress identify activities that serve as alternatives to addictions, foster interpersonal skills such as trust, cooperation, and teamwork, enhance self-esteem through realization success with a given pursuit, increase access to new social environments, foster new interests, negotiate constraints, develop awareness of personal needs and appropriate avenues

⁶⁶ NCSA (n1) ss 2(1)(c), 4(2)(b), 10(e)(f),14; ACJA (n1) ss 311(2)(a), 401(2)(c), 460(4)(b); Ouagadougou Declaration (n1) paras 1, 3; UNSMR (n1) r 4(1)(2).

⁶⁷ Ojukwu(n51) 11.

⁶⁸ Amnesty International (n53) 28.

⁶⁹ ACHPR(n5) art 22(2); UNDRD (n6) arts 1(1), 2(1), 8(1); Basic Principles (n6) prin 6.

⁷⁰ CFRN(n5) s 17(3)(d).

⁷¹ NPSSO (n7) ords 381(a)(e), 387.

⁷² *Ibid*, s 381(e).

⁷³ UDHR (n5) art 24.

⁷⁴ UNSMR (n1) rr 23, 105.

⁷⁵ *Ibid*, r 23(2).

⁷⁶ M R Alexander, *Correctional Recreation: An Overview* (Murray State University Centre for Adult and Reginal Education 2017) 11.

⁷⁷ Alexander (n76).

⁷⁸ *Ibid*.

⁷⁹ A Caplan, *The Role of Recreational Sports in the Federal Prison System* (Acadia University Publication 1996) 8.

to satisfy them, develop decision-making and problem solving skills and develop new interest which could evolve into a career.⁸⁰

The right to creation and leisure is an invaluable right of the Nigerian inmate which enables him to have a reformed mind and thinking which allows for proper reintegration into the society. However, the limited application of this right to convicted inmates and young persons,⁸¹ amount to an infraction of the right of awaiting trial inmates. Again, the National Human Rights Commission reports that most of the correctional centres visited has indoor and outdoor sporting activities, such as Football, Volley Ball, Table Tennis, Ludo and cards for recreation/leisure but were inadequate and some has no recreational facilities.⁸² These obvious denial of the right to recreation/leisure of the awaiting trial inmates and the inadequate provision of the recreation/leisure facilities for the Nigerian inmates contravenes the rights of the inmates protected under relevant laws.⁸³

2.4 Right to Work/Wages

The right to work and earn wages of the Nigerian inmates as against forced labour,⁸⁴ is essential to the rehabilitation and reintegration of the inmates into the society. The Nigerian inmates right to work and earn wages is protected by the Nigerian constitution,⁸⁵ Nigerian Correctional Service Act,⁸⁶ African Charter⁸⁷ and Nigerian Prisons Service Standing Orders.⁸⁸ Thus, Section 17(3)(a)(b) of the CFRN opined that, 'all citizens, without discrimination on any group whatsoever, shall have adequate opportunity to secure suitable employment, which the condition of work shall be just and humane'. Section 14(1)(3) of the NCSA also adumbrates that, 'the correctional service shall provide opportunities for training in modern farming techniques and animal husbandry for inmates which shall be administered to encourage generation of funds to aid the earning scheme for the inmates. Moreso, Section 10(h) of the NCSA reiterated that, 'the custodial service has the obligation to empowering inmates through the deployment of educational and vocational skills training programmes, and facilitating incentives and income generation through Custodial Centres, farms and industries. Accordingly, the Controller-General shall approve the sharing of revenue due to the correctional service from any enterprise, provided that one-third shall each be set aside for the inmates participating in the activity.'⁸⁹ Again, Article 15 of the ACHPR declare that every individual, including the Nigerian inmates, 'shall have the right to work under equitable and satisfactory conditions, and shall receive equal pay for equal work'.

Further, at the international scene, the right of the Nigerian inmate to work and wages is guaranteed by the Universal Declaration of Human Rights,⁹⁰ International Covenant on Economic Social and Cultural Rights,⁹¹ United Nations Standard Minimum Rules⁹² and United Nations Basic Principles.⁹³ Thus, Article 23(1)(2) of the UDHR, which is similar in provision with Article 6(1) of the ICESCR opined that, 'everyone has a right to work and without discrimination to equal pay for equal work'. Work must be decent in the sense that it should respect the fundamental rights of the human person as well as the right

⁸⁰ M J Carter and J K Russell, 'What is the Perceived North of Recreation? Results from Country Jail Study' [2005](67)(3) *Corrections Today*, 81.

⁸¹ NPSSO (n7) s 381(a).

⁸² Ojukwu (n51)11.

⁸³ CFRN(n5) s 17(3)(d); UDHR (n5) art 24; UNSMR (n1) rr 23, 105.

⁸⁴ *Ibid*, s 34(1)(b)(c); International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights 1966, art 8; NCSA (n1) s 15(1).

⁸⁵ *Ibid*, s 17(3)(a)(b).

⁸⁶ NCSA (n1) ss 10(h), 14(1)(3)(4)(a).

⁸⁷ ACHPR (n5) art 15.

⁸⁸ NPSSO (n7) ord 167.

⁸⁹ NCSA (n1) s 14(4)(a).

⁹⁰ UDHR (n5) art 23.

⁹¹ ICESCR (n5) arts 5, 7.

⁹² UNSMR (n1) rr 96, 98.

⁹³ Basic Principles (n6) prin 8.

of the workers such as, among others, the right to just remuneration.⁹⁴ Rule 96 of the UNSMR also adumbrates that sentenced inmates, 'shall have the opportunity to work'. So far as possible the work provided shall be such as will maintain or increase the inmates ability to earn honest living⁹⁵ According, there shall be a system of equitable remuneration of work of inmates.⁹⁶ Moreso, Principle 8 of the Basic Principles declare that, 'conditions shall be created enabling inmates to undertake meaningful remunerated employment which will facilitate their reintegration into the country's labour market and permit them to contribute to their own financial support and to that of their family'. Thus, the Indian Supreme Court in *Mohammad Ghiasuddin v State of Andhra Pradesh*,⁹⁷ held that inmate has a right to be paid a reasonable wage for the work done in the correctional centres. In *Re-Prison Reforms Enforcement of Wages of Prisoners*,⁹⁸ the Indian Supreme Court declares that the hiring of the Convicts and not paying them properly for their work amounts to forced labour and is a violation of Article 23 of the Indian Constitution. Again, in *Olga Tellis v Bombay Municipality Corporation*,⁹⁹ the Indian Supreme Court held that an important facet of the right to life is the right to livelihood, because no person can live without the means of livelihood. The same reasoning was employed by the Inter-American Court of Human Rights in the Indigenous Community of *Yakye Axa v Paraguay*,¹⁰⁰ where the Court held that the prevention of access to the applicant's traditional means of livelihood was a violation of the right to life.

Thus, inmates should be allowed to a remunerated work for them to spend part of the wages in the correctional centre, send part to their families and to save some part for their release. However, the provision of Order 167 of the NPSSO which states that, earning scheme is a privilege that an inmate enjoys as a result of good conduct and industry and shall only apply to inmates serving long sentence ranging from three year and above is a contravention of the right of the Nigerian inmates to work. The provision is itself is limited to a class of inmates and it is therefore discriminatory.

The right to work and wages should be applicable to all inmates in the correctional centre. The rationale for this right is that once an inmate has no work and becomes idle, they may lose their sense of responsibility for themselves and their family as this may make it difficult for them to live a law-abiding life after their release. Accordingly, the provision of Order 167 of the NPSSO, which allows the denial of the right to work and earn wages of the Nigerian inmates is antithetical to the right of these Nigerian inmates to work and earn wages protected under the relevant laws.¹⁰¹

2.5 Right to Communication with the Outside World

The right of the Nigerian inmates to communication with the outside world is implicit in the right to reformation and rehabilitation. The component of this right is the receiving of visitors and communication. These right aids the reformation and rehabilitation of the Nigerian inmates and reintegration into the society. This right is protected by the Nigerian Correctional Service Act,¹⁰² Nigerian Prisons Service Standing Orders,¹⁰³ Robben Island Guidelines¹⁰⁴ and Kampala Declaration.¹⁰⁵ Thus, section 21(1) of the NCSA guarantees visitation of the Nigerian inmates in custodial centres by official visitors consisting of ex-officio who shall be appointed by the President, consisting Chief justice of

⁹⁴ UN Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights. 'General Comment No.18: The Right to work-E/C.12/GC/18/2005<<https://www.escr.net/doc/gcE/c/12/GC/182005>> accessed 16 February, 2026.

⁹⁵ UNSMR (n1) r 98(1).

⁹⁶ UNSMR (n1), r 103(1).

⁹⁷ AIR 1978 SC 153; *State of Gujarat v Hon'ourable High Court of Gujarat* AIR 1998 SC 3169.

⁹⁸ AIR 1966 SC 424.

⁹⁹ (1985) 2 SCR 51.

¹⁰⁰ (2005) Inter-Am. Ct. H.R. (Ser. C) No. 125, 6.

¹⁰¹ CFRN (n5) s 17(3)(a)(b); NSCA (n1) ss 10(h), 14(1)(3)(4)(a); ACHPR (n5) art 15; UDHR (n5) art 23; ICESCR (n5) art 6,7; UNSMR (n1) rr 96, 98; Basic Principles (n5) prin 8.

¹⁰² NCSA (n1) ss 21, 22.

¹⁰³ NPSSO (n7) ords 146, 159, 400.

¹⁰⁴ Robben Island Guideline and Measures for the Prohibition and Prevention of Torture, Cruel Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment 2002, art 34.

¹⁰⁵ Kampala Declaration (n5) para 6.

Nigerian and other Justices of the Supreme Court, President of the Court of Appeal and other Justices of the Court of Appeal, Chief Judge and other Judges of the Federal High Court, Chairperson and other Council Members of the National Human Right Commission and so on. The official visitors are empowered to inspect the condition of treatment of inmates and receive complaints of the inmates.¹⁰⁶ Further, Order 400 of the NPSSO guarantees the communication between the inmate, his relations and legal adviser which shall be approved by the Superintendent-in-Charge. Accordingly, inmates can communicate through letter writing.¹⁰⁷ Moreso, Order 159 of the NPSSO adumbrates that, 'every correctional centre shall have a suitable place for visit for inmates, their friends or relatives'. Again, Article 34 of the Robben Island Guidelines declares that State parties are to ensure that all persons deprived of their liberty have access to legal services and have the right to be visited by and correspond with family members'. Moreso, Paragraph 6 of the Kampala Declaration opined that inmates, 'should be given the opportunity to maintain and develop links with their facilities and the outside world, and in particular be allowed access to lawyers'.

The right of the Nigerian inmates to communicate with the outside world is further protected by the United Nations Standard Minimum Rules¹⁰⁸ and United Nations Body of Principles.¹⁰⁹ Thus, Rule 58(1) of the UNSMR declare that inmates, 'shall be allowed, under necessary supervision, to communicate with their family and friend at regular intervals and by corresponding in writing and using, where available, telecommunication, electronic, digital and other means and by receiving visits'. Again, Principle 15 of the Body of Principles opined that, 'communication of the detained or imprisoned person with the outside world, shall not be denied for more than a matter of days. Accordingly, a detained or imprisoned person shall have the right to be visited by and to correspond with, in particular, members of his family and shall be given adequate opportunity to communicate with the outside world.'¹¹⁰

However, the Nigerian correctional authorities are sometimes found wanting in a lot of restrictions and controls that are placed on the inmates so much so that the whole atmosphere for such visit and communication become generally uncondusive,¹¹¹ thereby affecting their reformative and rehabilitative rights. Amnesty international reports also that inmates have little contact with the outside world.¹¹² The right to contact with the outside world should still remain a right that an inmate should enjoy despite the fact that he is put in a legal custody.¹¹³ The infraction of such a right of the inmates by the correctional authorities is tantamount to depriving the inmates one of his fundamental rights.¹¹⁴ Accordingly, the Indian supreme court has ruled in *Francis Coralie Mullian v Administrator Union Territory of Delhi*,¹¹⁵ that inmates could meet and interview family members, friends, and lawyers without strict legal restrictions, and in certain cases be allowed to leave the correctional centres and visit family members.

3 CONCLUSION

The Nigerian inmates' rights to reformation, rehabilitation and reintegration back into the society to lead a crime free life which is the modern thrust to penological objectives is guaranteed and protected by relevant correctional laws.¹¹⁶ The right of the Nigerian inmates to education/vocational training,¹¹⁷

¹⁰⁶ NCSA (n1) s 22(1).

¹⁰⁷ NPSSO (n7) ord 146.

¹⁰⁸ UNSMR (n1) r 58(1).

¹⁰⁹ Body of Principles (n5) prin 15, 18(3), 19.

¹¹⁰ *Ibid*, prin 19.

¹¹¹ N J Udombana, 'Advancing the Well Being of the Vulnerable: Law and Women Prisoners in Nigeria' [2007](v)(1) *Lagos State University Law Journal*, 129.

¹¹² Amnesty International (n53) 31.

¹¹³ M A Arorami, 'Prisoners Rights Under Nigerian Law: Legal Pathways to Progressive Realization and Protection' [2015](6)(1) *Afe Babalola University Journal of Sustainable Development Law and Policy*, 191.

¹¹⁴ *Ibid*.

¹¹⁵ AIR 1978 SC 153.

¹¹⁶ NSCA (1) ss 2(1)(c), 4(2)(6), 10(e)(d), 14; ACJA(n1) ss 311(2)(a), 401(2)(c), 460(4)(b); Ouagadougou Declaration (n1) paras 1, 3; UNSMR (n1) r 4(1)(2).

development,¹¹⁸ recreation/leisure,¹¹⁹ work/wages,¹²⁰ including communication with the outside world are the derivatives of the Nigerian inmates rights to reformation, rehabilitation and reintegration back into the society to lead a crime free life. The violation or contraventions of these rights by the Nigerian authorities is a direct infringement on the right of the Nigerian inmates to reformation, rehabilitation and reintegration into the society.

The rights of the Nigerian inmates to reformation, rehabilitation and reintegration into the society have been contravened in several ways by the Nigerian authorities.¹²¹ There are thus reports of inadequate educational/vocational training for the inmates in the Nigerian correctional centres.¹²² The Nigerian correctional centres libraries also lack professional Librarians.¹²³ Moreso, most correctional centres lacks recreation/leisure activities relevant to the protection of the Nigerian inmates right to reformation, rehabilitation and reintegration into the society.¹²⁴ Again, the Nigerian inmates rights to work/earn wages is also of a limited application.¹²⁵

The Nigerian authorities, particularly, the Nigerian Correctional Service, are empowered to take responsibility to protecting the right of the Nigerian inmates to reformation, rehabilitation and reintegration back into the society. These rights should be protected through education/vocational training, recreation/leisure, development, work/wages and communication with the outside world.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Adequate provisions should be made for the educational and vocational training of inmates in the Nigerian correctional centres which should be integrated into public schools and educational system of the country to enable the inmates to continue in their education and vocational training even after release without difficulty.
2. The Nigerian Correctional Service in collaboration with the National Open University of Nigeria should establish a Special Study Centre in at least one correctional centre in each state of the federation to enable the Nigeria inmates to attend tertiary institutions. This will aid speedy reformation and rehabilitation of the Nigerian inmates.
3. The Nigerian Correctional Service should allow all inmates in the Nigerian correctional centres to work and earn wages and make adequate provisions for recreation/leisure to activate the reformation and rehabilitation of the Nigerian inmates.
4. The Nigerian Correctional Service should allow inmates in the Nigerian correctional centres to communicate with their relatives, friends and so on, without much bottleneck to enhance the reformation and rehabilitation of the Nigerian inmates.

¹¹⁷ CFRN (n5) s 18(1)(3); ACHPR (n5) art 17(1); NCSA (n1) ss 10(h), 14; Kampala Declaration (n5) para 7; UDHR (n5) art 26(1); ICESCR (n5) art 13(1); UNSMR (n1) rr 4(2), 98(1), 104; Body of Principles (n5) prin 28.

¹¹⁸ ACHPR(n5) art 22; UNDRD (n6) arts 1, 2(1), 8(1); Basic Principles (n6) prin 6.

¹¹⁹ CFRN(n5) s 17(3)(d); NPSSO (n7) ords 381(a)(e), 387; UDHR (n5) art 24; UNSMR (n1) rr 23, 105.

¹²⁰ CFRN (n5) s 17(3)(a)(b); NCSA (n1) ss 10(h), 14(1)(3)(4)(a); ACHPR (n5) art 15; NPSSO (n7) ord 167; UDHR (n5) art 23; ICESCR (n5) arts 5, 7; UNSMR (n1) rr 96, 98; Basic Principles (n6) prin 8.

¹²¹ Ojukwu (n51); Amnesty International (n53).

¹²² *Ibid.*

¹²³ *Ibid.*

¹²⁴ *Ibid.*

¹²⁵ NPSSO (n7) ord 167.